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Title: Ultrasound guided brachiocephalic vein cannulation in children - first experience

Author(s): Sonja Vuletic, Biljana Draskovic, Goran Rakic, Anna Uram-Benka, Izabella Fabri, Marina Pandurov, Danica Stanic, Institute for child and youth healthcare of Vojvodina, Novi Sad, Serbia

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US guided BCV cannulation in children-first experience

Sonja Vuletić¹, Biljana Drašković^{1,2}, Goran Rakić^{1,2}, Anna Uram-Benka^{1,2}, Izabella Fabri^{1,2}, Marina Pandurov¹,
Danica Stanić¹,

¹ Institute for the healthcare of children and youth of Vojvodina, Clinic of Pediatric surgery, Department for pediatric anesthesia, Intensive care and pain therapy, Novi Sad, Republic of Serbia

² University of Novi Sad, Faculty of Medicine, Novi Sad, Republic of Serbia

Introduction: Central venous catheter (CVC) insertion in infants and children is a challenge even for the experienced anaesthetist. Ultrasound guided (US) CVC insertion is a safe method. Studies showed that the subclavian vein may be preferred in children, due to its low infection rate. The brachiocephalic vein (BCV) can be observed with US by a supraclavicular approach. In our study we present the the first 60 cases of ultrasound guided CVC placement in the BCV.

Aim: Our aim was to evaluate this tehniqe which was new to our department. We observed the whole process of placement, maintenance and duration.

Methods: In our study in all children, CVC was placed in the BCV guided by ultrasoud (GE® Venue 40, US machine). A supraclavicular approach was used, and the CVC was inserted in the operating theatre using a Seldinger method with an in-plane technique. Number of punctions, complications, insertion success rate and need for RTG confirmation were observed. We also observed the duration period and the indications for catheter removal.

Results: The results of the study showed that the CVC's were inserted mainly at first attempt ($p < 0,05$). Only premature infants required more that one punction (8,3% pateints) and RTG confirmation. There were no complications during the insertion process, and the success rate was 100%. The catheters lasted from 1 - 33 days, and were removed because of various reasons. Only in one patient the CVC was removed due to infection. In several patients a tunnelled CVC was placed in the BCV, and these catheters lasted significantly longer (>54 days).

Conclusion: We concluded that an US guided CVC insertion in the BCV is a safe method which is easy to learn. The rate of infection related to CVC was minimal.